

EFFECTIVENESS AND ACCEPTABILITY OF AI AS A TOOL IN ASSESSING STUDENT ESSAYS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effectiveness and acceptability of ChatGPT in assessing student essays at Occidental Mindoro State College – Basic Education Laboratory during the school year 2025-2026. Employing a descriptive-comparative quantitative research design, this study aimed to examine teachers' and students' perceptions of ChatGPT's effectiveness in terms of content, organization, language, and coherence, and acceptability in terms of accuracy, efficiency, convenience, and reliability. The study encompassed 36 teachers and 300 junior high school students, selected through total enumeration. Data were collected using an expert-validated, researcher-developed questionnaire that uses a four-point Likert scale. Descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) summarized the data, whereas inferential statistics (Mann-Whitney U Test and Kruskal-Wallis H Test with Post Hoc pairwise comparisons) identified the significant differences in perceptions of the tool's effectiveness and acceptability across profile variables and among the groups of respondents. Findings revealed that both teachers and students perceived ChatGPT as effective and acceptable for assessing student essays, with language and convenience being the highest-rated indicators, respectively. Meanwhile, demographic factors do not influence teachers' perceptions of the tool, while grade level and ChatGPT usage frequency factor in the students' perceptions. On the other hand, there are no statistically significant differences in the perceptions of both groups regarding the tool's effectiveness and acceptability. As an output of this study, a policy paper was developed as a basis for the ethical and pedagogically sound integration of ChatGPT in assessing written outputs, particularly essays.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence, ChatGPT, student essays, effectiveness, acceptability*

INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly growing digital world, the use of technology and Artificial Intelligence has paved the way and gained significance, making things easier and more innovative. In the educational milieu, the integration of AI in formative assessment practices in language learning is one of the numerous areas that these technological advancements have remarkably transformed. AI-integrated formative assessments are tools that utilize AI to enhance and innovate ongoing assessments conducted in classrooms, focusing on the monitoring of students' learning progress and the provision of continuous feedback. Educators use this feedback to enhance their teaching practices (Owan et al., 2023).

Nowadays, numerous AI applications are being used by educators to facilitate formative assessments, particularly in the context of English language learning (Savas, 2025). Among those AI applications, ChatGPT is one of the most prevalent and extensively used AI tools among teachers and students alike due to its multiple potential uses in language learning. It gives prompt, straightforward responses to search queries, assists students with creative writing, brainstorming, and coming up with new ideas, provides individualized tutoring and explanations, helps students understand concepts, answer questions, summarizes information, helps students prepare for tests, and aids teachers in assessment purposes (Mosaiyebzadeh et al., 2023).

Speaking of assessment purposes, particularly for written assessments, ChatGPT can support teachers in grading and offering constructive feedback on students' writing. In the study of Anu and Ansah (2023), they highlighted the multiple advantages of using ChatGPT as a support with written assessment marking, such as boosting consistency, removing human subjectivity-related biases, generating feedback for a wide cohort, and facilitating a quicker grading procedure and increased accuracy through constant evaluation, that is, marking the same assessment more than once.

Despite the advantages of ChatGPT in grading and giving feedback to written assessments, a significant gap remains in exploring the actual effectiveness and acceptability of ChatGPT in formative assessments, specifically in essay writing, where nuances in content, organization, language, and coherence are crucial. In addition, while several studies have scrutinized the universal utilization of AI in education, there is still a notable gap that remains in exploring how teachers and students perceive ChatGPT as an AI-integrated formative assessment tool, particularly as a tool in assessing essays. It remains uncertain whether they regard ChatGPT as a reliable and efficient tool for providing feedback that can guide students with paper revisions and improve their writing skills (Manning et al., 2025; Marzuki et al., 2025).

This gap becomes even more urgent due to the increasing workload of teachers and the growing number of students, which makes it difficult to provide timely and individualized feedback on students' essays. Based on the researcher's experience, given the numerous tasks and responsibilities of teachers, including managing multiple classes, lesson planning, administrative tasks, and extracurricular activities, each leaves a limited amount of time for providing efficient and consistent feedback on formative essay

assessments. These lead teachers to use AI tools like ChatGPT to assist with checking grammar and coherence and to provide initial comments and suggestions.

Notably, both teachers and students in the local context are gradually relying on ChatGPT to improve and assess essays, whether as a self-checking tool or a grading assistant. However, the effectiveness and acceptability of this practice have not been explored, specifically from both groups' perspectives and within the Philippine educational context. Thus, this study aimed to close this gap by exploring the effectiveness and acceptability of ChatGPT as a formative assessment tool in assessing essays, particularly from the perspectives of both teachers and students. To elucidate, it investigated both groups' perspectives on the performance of ChatGPT in assessing the core components of essay writing, like content, organization, language, and coherence, and how they perceive the tool's accuracy, efficiency, convenience, and reliability. By examining these aspects, this study aimed to bridge the gap between the actual utilization of AI in the classroom and the existing body of research, eventually contributing to the informed and purposeful integration of AI in educational assessment.

With an emphasis on assessing essays in the language classroom, the language teachers and the junior high school students in San Jose, Occidental Mindoro, were chosen because of their expertise in evaluating students' written works and their direct experience with using ChatGPT as an AI-integrated formative assessment tool. On the other hand, the results of this study can shed light on ChatGPT's potential as an automated essay grading and feedback tool in the language classroom, as well as its drawbacks and areas of improvement. Furthermore, the findings of this study may also serve as a foundation for further studies regarding the use of ChatGPT for assessment purposes. Therefore, this study was conducted.

Research Questions

This study aimed to examine the effectiveness and acceptability of AI, specifically ChatGPT, as a tool in assessing student essays.

Particularly, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Teacher-Respondents
 - a) age;
 - b) sex;
 - c) years of teaching experience;
 - d) highest educational attainment; and
 - e) frequency of ChatGPT usage?
 - 1.2 Student-Respondents
 - a) sex;
 - b) grade level; and
 - c) frequency of ChatGPT usage?

2. What is the level of effectiveness of ChatGPT in assessing student essays, as assessed by the two groups of respondents, in terms of:
 - a) content;
 - b) organization;
 - c) language; and
 - d) coherence?
3. What is the level of acceptability of the two groups of respondents in using ChatGPT for assessing student essays in terms of:
 - a) accuracy;
 - b) efficiency;
 - c) convenience; and
 - d) reliability?
4. Is there any significant difference in the teacher-respondents' perceived level of effectiveness of ChatGPT when grouped according to profile?
5. Is there any significant difference in the teacher-respondents' perceived level of acceptability of ChatGPT when grouped according to profile?
6. Is there any significant difference in the student-respondents' perceived level of effectiveness of ChatGPT when grouped according to profile?
7. Is there any significant difference in student-respondents' perceived level of acceptability of ChatGPT when grouped according to profile?
8. Is there a significant difference in the effectiveness of ChatGPT in assessing student essays, as assessed by the two groups of respondents?
9. Is there a significant difference in the acceptability of ChatGPT in assessing student essays by the two groups of respondents?
10. What policy recommendation can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a descriptive-comparative quantitative research design to examine the perceived effectiveness and acceptability of AI use, particularly ChatGPT, in assessing essays. According to Creswell and Creswell (2018), the descriptive-comparative research design is a research approach aimed at comparing two or more groups or variables to describe the characteristics evident in them and to determine their possible differences or relationships. On the other hand, the population comprised 36 language teachers and 300 junior high school students in San Jose, Occidental Mindoro. It was undertaken during the Academic Year 2025-2026. Teachers and students were included as they are both directly involved in the essay assessment. Meanwhile, total enumeration was used to include all available teachers and students, ensuring comprehensive data on the effectiveness and acceptability of ChatGPT in assessing essays. This approach ensured complete coverage of all qualified respondents. This is a kind of purposive sampling method being applied when the entire population is limited in size and possesses defined characteristics, as examining only a subset may not accurately yield the intended data. This approach minimizes any potential bias that is associated with other sampling techniques (Thomas, 2021).

The research instrument used in this study was a researcher-made survey questionnaire using a four-point Likert scale with hypothetical mean scores ranging from 1.00 to 4.00. The questionnaire was divided into three main sections: (1) personal information, (2) effectiveness of ChatGPT in assessing student essays, and (3) acceptability of ChatGPT in assessing student essays. The questionnaire was subjected to validation by a panel of experts, which included a language educator, a research expert, and an educational technology expert at the University of Perpetual Help System DALTA and Occidental Mindoro State College. Then, a pilot test was administered to 15 language teachers and 15 high school students who would not serve as the actual respondents of the study but shared common attributes. For instance, teachers were selected because they (1) are currently teaching English or any language-related subject in Junior or Senior High School, (2) have at least one year of experience in assessing student essays, and (3) have used ChatGPT at least three times for reviewing, providing feedback, and evaluating essays. Meanwhile, students were selected because they (1) are currently enrolled in Grades 7 to 10, (2) have written essays as part of the academic requirements, and (3) have used ChatGPT at least three times in total, including any combination of writing, editing, and receiving feedback on their essays.

In this study, the researcher collected the data through an online survey using the following procedures: First, the researcher developed a questionnaire designed to collect the necessary data for the study. Then, the questionnaire underwent validation. Afterward, once finalized, the researcher formally sought approval from the concerned school head by sending a letter of request for permission to conduct the survey. After securing the approval, the researcher pursued informed consent from the respondents and explained that the data gathered from them would be treated with strict confidentiality. Afterward, the respondents were given the survey questionnaire through Google Forms. Lastly, after all the responses have been collected, the researcher tallied, analyzed, and interpreted them in accordance with the specific issues outlined.

To address the problems of this study, descriptive statistics were employed to summarize and describe the demographic profile of the respondents and their responses regarding their perspectives or evaluations of the effectiveness and acceptability of using ChatGPT in assessing essays. Specifically, this included the computation of frequencies and percentages to present the demographic profile of the respondents, as well as the calculation of mean and standard deviation to analyze the responses of the respondents to the Likert-scale items in the questionnaire, determining their evaluations or perspectives of the effectiveness and acceptability of using ChatGPT in assessing student essays. The mean indicated the average response, while the standard deviation indicated the consistency of the responses in the study.

Finally, inferential statistics were used to determine whether there are significant differences in the perspectives or evaluations of teachers and students regarding the effectiveness and acceptability of ChatGPT and when grouped according to profile. Non-parametric tests were utilized as the data did not meet several key assumptions required for parametric analysis. The distribution of responses demonstrated the presence of outliers and non-normality, making non-parametric procedures more suitable and

accurate. Thus, the Mann-Whitney U Test was utilized for comparisons between two independent groups. On the other hand, the Kruskal-Wallis H Test was used to compare three or more groups. When the Kruskal-Wallis H Test yielded significant results, a Post Hoc Analysis (pairwise comparisons) was employed to identify the specific groups that demonstrated significant differences in their perceptions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: What is the demographic profile of respondents in terms of:

1.1 Teacher-Respondents

Table 1
Profile of the Teacher-Respondents

Profile	Frequency (n= 36)	Percentage
Sex		
Male	9	25.00%
Female	27	75.00%
Age		
Emerging Adulthood (18-29 years old)	25	69.44%
Young Adulthood (30 – 39 years old)	7	19.44%
Middle Adulthood (40 – 65 years old)	4	11.11%
<i>Median Age</i>	25.50	
Teaching Experience		
1 – 10 years	23	63.89%
11 – 20 years	10	27.78%
20 years and beyond	3	8.33%
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor’s Degree	17	47.22%
Master’s Degree	15	41.67%
Doctoral Degree	4	11.11%
Frequency of ChatGPT Usage		
Occasionally	15	41.67%
Frequently	21	58.33%

Table 1 presents the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents. In terms of age, the results indicated that the majority of the teacher-respondents were under emerging adulthood (69.44%). This is followed by young adulthood (19.44%) and middle adulthood (11.11%), respectively. Meanwhile, the median age was 25.50, suggesting that the majority of the teacher-respondents are likely young teachers who fall within the age range of digital natives. The results also imply that the teacher-respondents in the study are primarily early-career, technology-literate professionals who were born with and exposed to digital and AI tools and applications. Digital natives are a term often used to

describe those who grew up in an era (primarily from 1980 onward) when digital technologies were prevalent, resulting in them becoming accustomed, comfortable, and fluent in those technologies from early life (Mertala et al., 2024). Meanwhile, when it comes to the age range of ChatGPT users, Ruby (2023) found that individuals aged 18-34 make up the majority of users, accounting for 56.61% of the total population. On the other hand, the smaller proportion of older teachers suggests that traditional or experience-based assessment practices may be less prevalent among the teacher-respondents, given that younger generations tend to explore and use AI tools more, such as ChatGPT (Babu et al., 2024).

Regarding sex, the results showed that most respondents were female, with a total percentage of 75%, while male teacher-respondents constituted only 25% of the total population. This implies that the teaching profession, in the context of the study, is dominated by females, which is aligned with national and international reports that regard females who compose the majority workforce in the education sector, as it is rooted in the traditional gender expectations that relate teaching with caregiving and nurturing responsibilities; thus, encouraging women to enter and stay in the profession (UNESCO, 2023). Consequently, it can be inferred that the overall perception of ChatGPT as a tool for assessing student essays may be influenced primarily by female teacher-respondents, who are characterized as open to innovative technologies while remaining mindful of their ethical implications.

In terms of the teaching experience, results revealed that teacher-respondents who had been teaching for over 1 to 10 years garnered the highest percentage of 63.89%, followed by 11 to 20 years of service with a total percentage of 27.78%, and 20 years of service and above with a total percentage of 8.33%, respectively. This implies that the majority of the teacher-respondents are early-career educators, suggesting a teacher workforce that is relatively early in its development and adaptation on its professional journey. According to Trust and Whalen (2020), novice and mid-career teachers are often in the adjustment phase, in which they are still exploring, experimenting with teaching methods and strategies, and building their own instructional identity and classroom management skills. Therefore, they are commonly open to adopting new technologies, particularly if these technologies provide convenience and support during their instructions. On the other hand, the minimal representation of highly experienced teachers suggests that long-tenured teachers may be less engaged in the use of innovative technologies in their teaching practices.

In terms of the highest educational attainment, almost half of the population of teacher-respondents hold a Bachelor's degree (47.22%), which makes it the most dominant group with regard to educational attainment. On the other hand, few teachers have pursued a Master's degree (41.67%), and some completed their Doctoral degree (11.11%). This implies that a significant proportion of the teacher-respondents in the context of the study have pursued postgraduate studies. Furthermore, this suggests that the majority of the respondents are academically qualified, and such a profile indicates that the group of teacher-respondents is competent to assess the performance of ChatGPT in relation to assessment principles. This is corroborated by the study by Sevim

and Akin (2021), which reported that teachers who pursued graduate studies were able to think critically, conduct research, teach and assess efficiently, relate theory to practice, and gain more profound knowledge in the field of teaching.

In terms of the frequency of ChatGPT usage, the majority of the teacher-respondents reported using it frequently (58.33%), while some utilized the tool occasionally (41.67%). This shows that most teachers have regularly incorporated ChatGPT into their teaching practices, such as lesson preparation and delivery, generating instructional materials, and creating and checking activities or assessments. In addition, the results also imply that teachers are developing confidence and becoming more practical in exploring the potential of AI tools like ChatGPT to enhance and innovate the teaching and learning process. In the same way, Mushthoza et al. (2023) revealed that AI tools like ChatGPT are being used by many educators to assess EFL settings, as these AI-based formative assessments automate score assignment and feedback delivery, leading to more consistent and better outcomes. Through these tools, feedback becomes more objective, teachers' workload is reduced, and they can focus more on other aspects of teaching that require significant time and effort.

1.2 Student-Respondents

Table 2
Profile of the Student-Respondents

Profile	Frequency (n=300)	Percentage
Sex		
Male	118	39.33%
Female	182	60.67%
Grade		
Grade 7	124	41.33%
Grade 8	89	29.67%
Grade 9	48	16.00%
Grade 10	39	13.00%
Frequency of ChatGPT Usage		
Occasionally	181	60.33%
Frequently	119	39.67%

Table 2 presents the profile of the student-respondents. In terms of sex, the results demonstrated that the majority of the student-respondents were female, accounting for the total percentage of 60.67%, while male student-respondents constituted the remaining 39.33% of the total population. This implies that the study's context is dominated by female students. Thus, their perceptions may shape the overall view of ChatGPT's use in assessing student essays. Studies have shown that compared to male students who freely utilize technologies or AI tools for completion of tasks and convenience, female students are more cautious and responsible when using these tools,

shared perception of ChatGPT as an essay assessment tool that can apply evaluation criteria consistently and in a structured manner, much like traditional assessment practices. Furthermore, the consistent high ratings across all criteria from teachers and students on its effectiveness imply that they perceive the tool as accurate and reliable, not only in surface-level evaluations but also in deeper aspects of writing, such as idea development and the logical flow of ideas. Such a finding is supported by Mizumoto (2024), whose study found that, in writing assessments in second-language classrooms, ChatGPT consistently corrects spelling and punctuation errors, demonstrating more substantial alignment with human judgments and improving students' writing scores.

Additionally, among the four aspects of essay writing and assessment, language is perceived as the highest by both teachers (mean=3.18, SD = 0.71) and students (mean=3.03, SD = 0.63) and interpreted as “effective.” This implies that both teachers and students demonstrate confidence in ChatGPT's ability to detect and correct grammatical errors, recognize poor word choices, and improve sentence clarity and construction. This aligns with the study by Huang et al. (2024), which found that ChatGPT can detect grammatical mistakes, awkward phrasing, limited vocabulary, structural issues affecting sentence clarity, and errors such as typos and spelling, just like how teacher raters assess the language of an essay. Meanwhile, content is perceived by teachers (mean=2.99, SD = 0.70) and students (mean=2.90, SD = 0.61) as the lowest yet is still considered “effective.” This means that teachers and students still recognize ChatGPT's commendable ability to identify the central idea, assess the scope and details, evaluate the relevance of supporting details or evidence, and provide precise feedback to improve the overall content of the essay. This aligns with the Atas et al. (2024) study, which found that, in terms of the essay's content criteria, ChatGPT provides precise evaluation and feedback that substantially resembles professors' grading comments.

Research Question 3: What is the level of acceptability of the two groups of respondents in using ChatGPT for assessing student essays?

Table 4
Level of Acceptability of ChatGPT of the Two Groups of Respondents in Using ChatGPT for Assessing Student Essays

Acceptability of ChatGPT	Teachers			Students		
	Mean	SD	Interpretation	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Accuracy	3.10	0.59	Acceptable	2.96	0.64	Acceptable
Efficiency	3.19	0.64	Acceptable	2.94	0.64	Acceptable
Convenience	3.22	0.66	Acceptable	2.99	0.66	Acceptable
Reliability	2.98	0.68	Acceptable	2.90	0.65	Acceptable
GRAND MEAN	3.12	0.59	Acceptable	2.95	0.58	Acceptable

Legend: 1.00 – 1.74 = Not Acceptable 1.75 – 2.49 = Slightly Acceptable;
2.50 – 3.24 = Acceptable 3.25 – 4.00 = Very Acceptable

Both teachers (grand mean = 3.12, SD = 0.59) and students (grand mean = 2.95, SD = 0.58) view ChatGPT as “Acceptable” as a tool for assessing student essays across

all areas, particularly in terms of accuracy, efficiency, convenience, and reliability. The relatively low standard deviations suggest that the responses were consistent within each group, indicating a shared view that ChatGPT is practical and useful for essay assessment tasks. This implies that teachers and students are open to incorporating ChatGPT into their assessment practices, specifically for assessing essays. The uniformity of acceptable ratings across the different areas also suggests that they regard the tool as practical and meaningful, helping streamline the process of assessing essays. This supports the findings of Sibug et al. (2024), who reported that Filipino teachers exhibit a positive attitude toward integrating AI tools, such as ChatGPT, into their classrooms. They also express their readiness and openness to adopting AI tools as part of their teaching practices, specifically to supplement and enhance their conventional instruction.

Among the indicators of acceptability, convenience is perceived as the highest by both teachers (mean=3.22, SD = 0.66) and students (mean=2.99, SD = 0.66) and interpreted as “acceptable.” This means that both teachers and students recognize the simple process of using the tool, how it evaluates essays instantly, and how easy its feedback is to understand. Such a finding is corroborated by the study of Yu et al. (2024), which stated that the convenience of using ChatGPT was one of the key factors shaping students' satisfaction and willingness to continue using it to accomplish their academic tasks. On the other hand, reliability is perceived by teachers (mean=2.98, SD = 0.68) and students (mean=2.90, SD = 0.65) as the lowest yet still considered “acceptable.” This suggests that they are open to using ChatGPT, as they perceive it as capable of generating unbiased, fair, consistent, and trustworthy evaluations across topics, writing styles, and multiple submissions. This finding aligns with the study by Li et al. (2024), which found that ChatGPT is highly reliable at assessing well-written work, as it can detect and distinguish diverse levels of sophistication and writing quality, indicating that it can justly and effectively assess essays of varying complexity.

Research Question 4: Is there any significant difference in the teacher-respondents' perceived level of effectiveness of ChatGPT when grouped according to profile?

Table 5
Significant Difference in the Teacher-Respondents' Perceived Level of Effectiveness of ChatGPT when Grouped according to Profile

Demographic Profile	t-value	p-value	Verbal Interpretation	“Decision”
Sex	135.50	.61	No significant difference	HO Accepted
Age	1.82	.40	No significant difference	HO Accepted
Teaching Experience	3.55	.17	No significant difference	HO Accepted
Educational Attainment	2.03	.36	No significant difference	HO Accepted

Frequency of ChatGPT Usage	136.00	.49	No significant difference	HO Accepted
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Legend: p-value <0.05 = Significant

The findings showed that there is no statistically significant difference in the teacher-respondents' perceived level of effectiveness when grouped according to age, sex, teaching, experience, educational attainment, and frequency of ChatGPT usage. This means that the teachers' age, sex, teaching experience, educational attainment, and frequency of usage do not factor into their perception of ChatGPT's effectiveness as an essay assessment tool. Thus, the null hypothesis is not rejected.

Specifically, regarding age, the results imply that, regardless of whether they are in emerging, young, or middle adulthood, the teacher-respondents have uniform exposure to and knowledge of integrating AI tools such as ChatGPT in education, particularly for assessment purposes. This is evident in the majority of the teacher-respondents reporting frequent use of the tool, suggesting that generational differences do not drive their perspectives. Likewise, the study of Fikri (2024) shares similar sentiments. The study's findings revealed that teachers across age brackets have greatly benefited from using ChatGPT in writing assessments. This is because teachers primarily use this tool to provide feedback during the learning process and assess their pupils' writing abilities.

In terms of sex, the results suggest that both male and female teachers report a similar level of perception regarding the effectiveness of AI tools, like ChatGPT, in their instruction and assessment practices. This suggests that both male and female teachers are equally engaged with the tool, resulting in their similar levels of perception about its effectiveness. This finding is consistent with the study by Cayak (2024), which noted that, regardless of sex, teachers have strong positive attitudes toward the efficiency of AI tools, such as ChatGPT, and minimal negative perceptions. These aspects reflect the teacher's increased readiness to integrate such tools into their teaching, learning, and assessment practices.

Meanwhile, regarding years of teaching experience, the findings imply that the teacher-respondents, regardless of 1-10, 11-20, or more than 20 years of teaching experience, share a similar stance regarding ChatGPT's effectiveness as an assessment tool. In line with this, Aziz and Khan (2025) emphasized that the integration of AI in education is being applied across various aspects of teaching and learning, aiming to innovate and enhance lesson delivery to learners, as well as improve learning outcomes. They also noted that multiple studies have shown that combining AI with traditional teaching methods in educational settings enhances service delivery by reducing administrative work, providing constructive feedback, personalizing learning, and improving accessibility.

In addition, in terms of the teachers' educational attainments, the findings imply that whether the teachers hold a bachelor's degree, a master's degree, or a doctoral degree, they still have the same views on ChatGPT's effectiveness. Likewise, Yu et al.

(2023) highlighted in their study that efficiency, high compatibility, and output quality are key attributes of ChatGPT that raise users' awareness of the tool's usefulness and ease of use, ultimately stimulating their interest in using it. Finally, in relation to the frequency of ChatGPT usage, the results also imply that the teacher-respondents have the same views regarding the tool's effectiveness, regardless of whether they use it frequently or occasionally. Even with minimal use of the tool, teachers can still acknowledge its steady performance in evaluating key aspects of writing. This is also supported by the study by Firaina and Sulisworo (2023), which found that although most teachers use ChatGPT frequently, they also recognize its limitations, as they sometimes observed that ChatGPT's responses were not aligned with their expectations, requiring them to verify the information or responses.

Research Question 5: Is there any significant difference in the teacher-respondents' perceived level of acceptability of ChatGPT when grouped according to profile?

Table 6
Significant Difference in the Teacher-Respondents' Perceived Level of Acceptability of ChatGPT when Grouped according to Profile

Demographic Profile	t-value	p-value	Verbal Interpretation	“Decision”
Sex	146.50	.36	No significant difference	HO Accepted
Age	2.12	.35	No significant difference	HO Accepted
Teaching Experience	3.86	.15	No significant difference	HO Accepted
Educational Attainment	2.75	.25	No significant difference	HO Accepted
Frequency of ChatGPT Usage	147.50	.75	No significant difference	HO Accepted

Legend: p-value <0.05 = Significant

The findings suggest that there is no statistically significant difference in the teacher-respondents' perceived level of acceptability when grouped according to age, sex, teaching, experience, educational attainment, and frequency of ChatGPT usage. This means that the teachers' age, sex, teaching experience, educational attainment, and frequency of usage do not play a crucial role in their perception of ChatGPT's acceptability as an essay assessment tool. Thus, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected.

In particular, regarding age, the findings suggest that most teachers, regardless of age differences, share the same positive attitudes toward the use of AI, such as ChatGPT, in assessing student essays. This may be because of the similarities in the frequency of usage of the tool by teachers, as the majority reported using ChatGPT frequently, which leads them to their consistent perceptions of its accuracy, efficiency, convenience, and reliability. However, in the study by Bakhadirov et al. (2024), they found a connection

between teachers' age and their adoption of AI in their teaching practices, suggesting that younger teachers are more open to using such tools than older ones. This is because younger teachers are usually more exposed to and familiar with digital tools and more flexible in adopting emerging innovative digital technologies in education.

The results also imply that sex does not play a pivotal role in shaping attitudes or openness of the teachers toward the utilization of AI, particularly ChatGPT, as an essay assessment tool. On the contrary, according to a study by Mutammimah et al. (2024), ease of use and perceived usefulness of ChatGPT positively influence male and female teachers' positive outlook on the tool, which becomes an indispensable factor in their decision to use it in their practices. They perceived that it is a meaningful and practical tool that they can use for English language teaching. Subsequently, in relation to the years of teaching experience, the results suggest that, regardless of the length of the experience of the teachers and whether they are novice or experienced teachers, they still hold comparable perceptions of ChatGPT's acceptability as a formative assessment tool. This is supported by the study of Koraishi (2024), who revealed that ChatGPT is being used by a wide range of users, like teachers, as it demonstrates the possibility of saving resources in educational assessment by simplifying the grading process, reducing the human raters' workloads, and enhancing the efficiency of grading.

Regarding the highest educational attainment, it implies that, regardless of pursuing different postgraduate degrees, such as a bachelor's, master's, or doctoral degree, teachers still express a willingness to use the tool for assessment purposes. Firat's study (2023) also revealed that teachers are open to using such a tool because pre-established rubrics integrated with ChatGPT for grading student essays help them assess student work more consistently and objectively. Aside from reducing bias and human error in essay assessment, this automated tool considerably lightens teachers' workload. Finally, in relation to the frequency of ChatGPT usage, the findings indicate that the frequency of usage of the teachers of the tool is not a factor that drives their acceptance of utilizing the tool in assessing student essays. The findings also align with those of Wang et al. (2021), who indicated that the perceived ease of use was one of the key determinants of teachers' willingness to utilize AI technologies. They suggested that if teachers are trained to use AI properly, their willingness to use the technology will tend to increase.

Research Question 6: Is there any significant difference in the student-respondents' perceived level of effectiveness of ChatGPT when grouped according to profile?

Table 7
Significant Difference in the Student-Respondents' Perceived Level of Effectiveness of ChatGPT when Grouped according to Profile

Demographic Profile	t-value	p-value	Verbal Interpretation	“Decision”
Sex	9665.50	.14	No significant difference	HO Accepted

Grade Level	22.74	<.01	With significant difference	HO Rejected
Frequency of ChatGPT Usage	13321.50	<.01	With significant difference	HO Rejected

Legend: p-value <0.05 = Significant

There is no statistically significant difference in the students' perceived level of effectiveness of ChatGPT as a tool in assessing student essays when grouped according to sex ($t = 9665.50$, $p = .14$). This implies that both male and female student-respondents share comparable views on the effectiveness of ChatGPT in assessing student essays. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the student-respondents' perceived level of effectiveness of ChatGPT as an essay assessment tool, when grouped according to sex, is retained. This finding aligns with the study by Bouzar et al. (2024), which found that male students tend to use ChatGPT more often than female students, as they find it valuable and easy to use. The results also showed that women tend to be more cautious about the use and potential consequences of this tool. Nevertheless, the same study emphasizes that both sexes acknowledge the educational value of ChatGPT, with no significant difference in their attitudes toward its effectiveness.

Furthermore, the analysis also revealed that there are significant differences in the students' perceived level of effectiveness of ChatGPT as a tool in assessing student essays when grouped according to grade level ($t = 22.74$, $p <.01$) and frequency of ChatGPT usage ($t = 13321.50$, $p <.01$). This means that the grade level and frequency of ChatGPT usage influence the students' perception of the acceptability of ChatGPT as essay checker. Thus, the null hypothesis regarding grade level and the frequency of ChatGPT usage is rejected. Particularly, the findings suggest that the students from the different grade levels do not hold similar views about how effective ChatGPT is when used to assess essays. This finding is corroborated by the study by Moybeka et al. (2023), which found that AI-driven chatbots, like ChatGPT, serve as companions to language learners on their learning journey. These tools hone their language skills and increase their engagement and confidence in language learning through personalized and interactive learning experiences.

Meanwhile, in relation to the frequency of ChatGPT usage, the findings mean that the students' perceptions of the effectiveness of ChatGPT differ depending on how often they use the tool. To elucidate, those who utilize the tool frequently are likely to view it as more effective for assessing essays because their regular usage allows them to become knowledgeable of its features and potential. On the other hand, students who use it less often may not fully appreciate its capabilities or remain vigilant about its accuracy, efficiency, convenience, and reliability, which results in lower effectiveness ratings. This result is consistent with a study by Ozcelik and Eksi (2024), who suggested that, with the use of the tool and an understanding of its full potential, students were able to recognize that although ChatGPT is valuable for assessing and correcting formal texts, it also has weaknesses. The students perceive that the tool lacks an educational approach, and some also expressed concerns about the tool's trustworthiness. Thus, the study recommended that, while several students agreed on the tool's potential for assessing

students' writing, it still needs improvement, particularly in providing suggestions and distinguishing different writing styles.

Significant Difference in the Effectiveness of ChatGPT as a Tool in Assessing Student Essays across Grade Levels

Since there is a statistically significant difference in students' perceived level of effectiveness of ChatGPT for essay assessment across grade levels, a post hoc pairwise comparison was conducted.

Table 8
Significant Difference in the Effectiveness of ChatGPT as a Tool in Assessing Student Essays across Grade Levels

Grade Level	t-value	p-value	Verbal Interpretation	“Decision”
10-8	30.548	.399	No significant difference	HO Accepted
10-7	62.597	<.001	With significant difference	HO Rejected
10-9	74.998	<.001	With significant difference	HO Rejected
8-7	32.049	.047	With significant difference	HO Rejected
8-9	-44.450	.025	With significant difference	HO Rejected
7-9	-12.401	1.000	No significant difference	HO Accepted

Legend: p-value <0.05 = Significant

The pairwise comparison of grade levels revealed several significant differences across student groups. Notably, significant differences were discovered between Grade 10 and Grade 7 ($t = 62.597$, $p < .001$), Grade 10 and Grade 9 ($t = 74.998$, $p < .001$), Grade 8 and Grade 7 ($t = 32.049$, $p = .047$), and Grade 8 and Grade 9 ($t = -44.450$, $p = .025$). These indicate that students at different grade levels do not have the same perceptions about how ChatGPT performed well in assessing essays. This pattern suggests that as students progress to higher grade levels, their familiarity with their learning tasks, writing expectations, and exposure to AI tools like ChatGPT may shape how they perceive the tool's effectiveness. Meanwhile, no significant differences were observed between Grades 10 and 8 ($t = 30.548$, $p = .399$) or between Grades 7 and 9 ($t = -12.401$, $p = 1.000$), suggesting that students in these grade levels have similar perceptions of ChatGPT's effectiveness in assessing essays.

Taken together, the mixed pattern of significant and non-significant differences underscores the crucial role that grade level plays in influencing how students rate the effectiveness of ChatGPT for essay assessment, but the distinction is not uniform across all grade groups. Aligned to this, the study by Polakova et al. (2024) underscores that in order to expand the benefits of ChatGPT in assessing written works, language educators should also consider addressing potential issues in the tool's utilization, such as the need to anchor its utilization on the needs of different students and lesson requirements for various levels, regulate it for specific linguistic phenomena, the risk of modifying assessments due to frequent text inputs, and ethical concerns.

Research Question 7: Is there any significant difference in student-respondents' perceived level of acceptability of ChatGPT when grouped according to profile?

Table 9

Significant Difference in the Student-Respondents' Perceived Level of Acceptability of ChatGPT when Grouped according to Profile

Demographic Profile	t-value	p-value	Verbal Interpretation	“Decision”
Sex	9582.50	.12	No significant difference	HO Accepted
Grade Level	18.09	<.01	With significant difference	HO Rejected
Frequency of ChatGPT Usage	12992.50	<.01	With significant difference	HO Rejected

Legend: p-value <0.05 = Significant

There is no statistically significant difference in the perceived level of acceptability of ChatGPT as a tool for assessing student essays when grouped according to sex ($t = 9582.50$, $p = .12$). This means that both male and female student-respondents have the same attitudes or willingness to accept and use ChatGPT as an assessment tool, particularly in written outputs. A possible explanation for this likeness is that both groups of student-respondents utilize ChatGPT at relatively similar frequencies. To elaborate, even though male student-respondents have reported a slightly higher number of regular ChatGPT users, and female student-respondents have reported a slightly higher number of occasional users, both sexes are generally accustomed but are not regarded as extremely dependent users. Therefore, since none of the groups utilizes ChatGPT extensively, their level of acceptability of using it remains moderate and reasonably aligned, resulting in no significant difference between them. Hence, the null hypothesis regarding this fails to be rejected.

However, in the study by Stohr et al. (2024), they found that there are noticeable differences in the perceptions across different groups of students by sex regarding the usage of AI tools like ChatGPT. For instance, female students tend to become less comfortable using AI as they have concerns about its effects on learning and assessment. This implies that sex or gender still plays a crucial role in the acceptance and adoption of AI tools like ChatGPT.

On the other hand, the analysis also disclosed that there are significant differences in the students' perceived level of acceptability of ChatGPT as a tool in assessing student essays when grouped according to grade level ($t = 18.09$, $p <.01$) and frequency of ChatGPT usage ($t = 12992.50$, $p <.01$). This suggests that the students' grade level and frequency of ChatGPT usage do factor in their perception of the tool's acceptability as an essay assessment tool. Hence, the null hypothesis of the difference in relation to the students' grade level and frequency of ChatGPT usage is rejected. Specifically, in terms of the grade level, the findings imply that the grade level of student-respondents affects how they perceive ChatGPT as acceptable in formative assessment purposes, specifically for essay assessments. These findings may be attributed to the differences in

cognitive maturity, academic expectations, and the frequency with which each grade level uses ChatGPT for writing purposes. In the study by Baek et al. (2024), it was found that older students or those in higher grade levels tend to be more open to using ChatGPT as an aid for academic tasks. The same study also indicated that many younger students, or those in lower levels, expressed fear of being penalized for using the tool. The older students or those in higher levels are likely to be more confident in utilizing the tool responsibly because of their academic experience, compared to the youngest group.

In relation to the frequency of ChatGPT usage, the results imply that the perceptions of the students with regard to ChatGPT's acceptability vary in accordance with their frequency of usage of the tool. This is corroborated by the study by Rueda (2023), which highlighted that several issues still need to be addressed in utilizing the tool, despite some teachers and students finding ChatGPT helpful for evaluating the accuracy of essay content. Upon being utilized by them, they perceived that ChatGPT still lacks extensive knowledge and has not been updated with recent information. As a result, the feedback from this tool might not always be accurate and specific, especially for specialized subjects.

Significant Difference in the Acceptability of ChatGPT as a Tool in Assessing Student Essays across Grade Levels

Since there is a statistically significant difference in students' perceived acceptability of ChatGPT for essay assessment across grade levels, a post hoc pairwise comparison was performed.

Table 10
Significant Difference in the Acceptability of ChatGPT as a Tool in Assessing Student Essays across Grade Levels

Grade Level	t-value	p-value	Verbal Interpretation	"Decision"
10-8	1.234	1.000	No significant difference	HO Accepted
10-7	4.915	.160	No significant difference	HO Accepted
10-9	5.397	.121	No significant difference	HO Accepted
8-7	8.176	.025	With significant difference	HO Rejected
8-9	3.513	.365	No significant difference	HO Accepted
7-9	.036	1.000	No significant difference	HO Accepted

Legend: p-value <0.05 = Significant

The pairwise comparison of grade levels showed that the perceived acceptability of ChatGPT varied slightly across student groups, with only a few differences statistically significant. As indicated in the table, significant differences were observed between Grade 8 and Grade 7 ($t = 8.176$, $p = .025$), which suggests that Grade 8 students perceived ChatGPT as more acceptable in assessing essays compared to Grade 7 students. On the other hand, no significant differences were exhibited between Grades 10 and 9 ($t = 5.397$, $p = .121$), Grades 10 and 8 ($t = 1.234$, $p = 1.000$), Grades 10 and 7 ($t = 4.915$, $p = .160$), Grades 8 and 9 ($t = 3.513$, $p = .365$) and Grades 7 and 9 ($t = .036$, $p = 1.000$),

indicating that students in these grade levels hold the same views on ChatGPT's acceptability in assessing essays.

Altogether, the results imply that the general perception of the students regarding ChatGPT's acceptability as a tool in assessing essays does not differ notably across grade levels. Aligned with this, Espartinez (2024) highlighted that as ChatGPT is being explored as a formative assessment tool that can provide grading and feedback on essays, especially in Philippine higher education institutions with sufficient technological support, it is crucial for teachers to make informed decisions on how to utilize the tool as part of the teaching and learning process to cater the needs and experiences of those who are impacted by its use, specifically the students.

Research Question 8: Is there a significant difference in the effectiveness of ChatGPT in assessing student essays, as assessed by the two groups of respondents?

Table 11
Significant Difference in the Effectiveness of ChatGPT in Assessing Student Essays, as Assessed by the Two Groups of Respondents

Groups	t-value	p-value	Verbal Interpretation	“Decision”
Teachers Students	4481.00	.10	No significant difference	HO Accepted

Legend: p-value <0.05 = Significant

There is no significant difference in the perceived effectiveness of ChatGPT as a tool for assessing student essays between the two groups of respondents: students and teachers ($t = 4481.00$, $p = .10$). Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the effectiveness of ChatGPT in assessing student essays, as assessed by the two groups of respondents, is not rejected. This means that both students and teachers have the same perceptions about the effectiveness of ChatGPT as a formative assessment tool for written works, particularly essays.

This similarity in the perceptions of the two groups of respondents may be attributed to their growing exposure to AI-assisted tools. The student-respondents, all junior high school students, are part of a generation immersed in digital environments, which makes them more open to and exposed to automated AI-assisted learning tools. Similarly, most of the teacher-respondents are early-to-mid-career educators, making them also considered digital natives, like the student-respondents, consistent with Babu et al. (2024) and Bouzar et al. (2024) who noted that younger generations, particularly younger millennials and Generation Z, like students and teachers, are more knowledgeable and inclined to use AI tools like ChatGPT in their daily and academic activities. They tend to express their appreciation for the utilization of AI tools like

ChatGPT for teaching and learning purposes because of their accessibility, convenience, usefulness, and immediacy.

Moreover, the absence of significant differences in the perspectives of students and teachers signifies that ChatGPT is not perceived as a student learning tool, nor a teacher aid or assistant, but both groups see it as a functional tool for giving grades, feedback, and evaluation to the written outputs of students, especially essays. This is aligned with the findings of numerous studies that AI-driven tools, such as ChatGPT, can offer accurate, efficient, and reliable feedback and evaluation to the works of students (Atas et al., 2024; Bucol and Sangkawong, 2024).

Research Question 9: Is there a significant difference in the acceptability of ChatGPT in assessing student essays by the two groups of respondents?

Table 12
Significant Difference in the Acceptability of ChatGPT in Assessing Student Essays by the Two Groups of Respondents

Groups	t-value	p-value	Verbal Interpretation	“Decision”
Teachers Students	4441.00	.08	No significant difference	HO Accepted

Legend: p-value <0.05 = Significant

The results revealed that there is no significant difference between the students' and teachers' perceived acceptability of using ChatGPT as a tool in assessing student essays ($t = 4441.00$, $p = .08$). Since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the acceptability of ChatGPT in assessing student essays, as assessed by the two groups of respondents, fails to be rejected. This implies that both students and teachers demonstrate a similar level of openness toward the utilization of ChatGPT in assessing student essays. This consistency in the perception between students and teachers may be influenced and explained by the familiarity and exposure of both groups of respondents to technology. To illustrate, the students in the context of the study are all junior high school students, who belong to Generation Z, a cohort widely considered as digital natives because of their upbringing in technology-driven environments where the internet, AI-assisted tools or applications, and the like are embedded in daily activities (Babu et al., 2024; Ruby, 2023).

Likewise, in the context of the study, the teacher-respondents were predominantly early- to mid-career teachers. It is a demographic closest to the students that is increasingly becoming comfortable and proficient in the use and integration of technology across different aspects. This aligns with the study by Chingakham (2024), which reported that many university educators, mostly holding master's or doctoral degrees, have begun integrating ChatGPT into lesson planning, resource development, and related activities. Finally, the findings also align with the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) by Davis

(1989), which underscores the two major factors, namely perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use, that influence a user's willingness to adopt a certain technology. In the study's context, both teachers and students find ChatGPT a helpful tool that simplifies and streamlines the assessment process by providing consistent, objective feedback on written outputs. As Wang et al. (2021) emphasized, perceived ease of use and performance benefits were key determinants of teachers' willingness to utilize AI technologies. They suggested that if teachers are trained on how to use AI, their willingness to use it properly will tend to increase.

Research Question 10: What policy recommendation can be proposed?

Based on the results and findings of the current study, which revealed that both teachers and students perceived ChatGPT as an effective and acceptable tool in assessing student essays, and that no significant differences were reported in their perceptions, a policy paper was developed. As the institution is committed to integrating innovative technologies to enhance teaching, learning, and assessment practices, a policy is hereby recommended that the institution formally adopt ChatGPT as a supplementary and optional digital tool in the classroom setting for assessing written works, such as essays, and improving the writing skills and performances of the students. This policy ignites the vision of the institution to foster high-quality education by integrating emerging educational tools or technologies responsibly and meaningfully into the teaching-learning process. Specifically, this policy seeks to:

1. Establish clear and specific guidelines for the responsible and pedagogically sound integration of AI tools, like ChatGPT, in teaching and learning practices, particularly in assessing writing tasks.
2. Enhance the accuracy, efficiency, and reliability of the assessment process by the informed usage of ChatGPT while retaining teachers' professional judgment as the basis for the evaluation.
3. Support teachers in giving timely, relevant, and objective feedback through continuous professional development and training about AI-assisted assessments.
4. Encourage responsible students' use of ChatGPT in their writing activities, fostering digital literacy, accountability, and creativity.
5. Develop institutional standards and quality assurance processes to monitor and evaluate the effectiveness, acceptability, and ethical compliance of the tool to the assessment practices.

Conclusions

The findings indicate that both teachers and students are sufficiently exposed to ChatGPT, enabling them to provide informed and meaningful evaluations of its potential in essay assessment. The results show that ChatGPT is capable of assessing the different areas of essay evaluation, demonstrating a remarkable potential in enhancing classroom formative assessment tasks and supplementing essay evaluation and feedback generation with teachers' evaluation. Its integration into existing assessment practices is generally viewed as convenient and acceptable, without causing significant challenges for the teachers and students. Regardless of sex, age, teaching experience,

educational attainment, and frequency of ChatGPT usage, teachers consistently perceive the tool as effective for assessing student essays, exhibiting its broad potential to enhance the essay assessment process across diverse teaching profiles. Students similarly view the tool as effective and acceptable across sexes; however, those in higher grade levels and with more frequent exposure report greater effectiveness and openness, indicating that academic maturity and familiarity influence students' evaluation of the tool.

Overall, both teachers and students recognize the tool's functionality in supporting and innovating essay assessment practices and express readiness to incorporate it into essay assessment practices. In line with the institution's commitment to integrating innovative technologies to enhance teaching, learning, and assessment, ChatGPT can serve as a supplementary and optional digital tool in the classroom setting for assessing written works, such as essays, and improving the writing skills and performances of the students.

Recommendations

The findings of this study suggest several implications for educational practice and future research. For students, schools may formally introduce ChatGPT as a supplementary or optional formative assessment tool to provide students with accurate, timely, and constructive feedback on their written outputs. Teachers may provide more guidance and supervision to lower-grade students in understanding the input generated by the tool. For students at higher grade levels, teachers may encourage independent use of the tool to cultivate self-assessment and metacognitive learning. For faculty members, teachers may utilize ChatGPT to provide initial feedback to the written outputs of the students to improve the accuracy and efficiency of the assessment process. However, the final evaluation of outputs may come from the teachers to guarantee accuracy, impartiality, and adherence to academic standards. Structured training and orientation sessions may also be provided to teachers, focusing on how to properly integrate ChatGPT into formative assessment practices.

For school administrators, they may establish institutional policies and guidelines that will specify when and how both teachers and students should use ChatGPT in teaching, learning, and assessment to avoid overdependence, uphold originality, and embrace the role of ChatGPT as an assistant tool. Curriculum developers may also consider the integration of AI literacy into English language education curricula. Learning modules or learning outcomes may be developed to promote the critical engagement of both teachers and students with AI tools, highlighting how technology can supplement instead of replacing human evaluation. Moreover, AI users may understand when and how to use ChatGPT to improve writing and assessment tasks without undermining originality and human creativity. Ethical guidelines and awareness campaigns for the responsible use of AI tools, such as ChatGPT, may be developed and implemented to educate AI users on ethical use. For future researchers, since the present study utilized a small number of teacher-respondents, they may replicate the study with a larger and more diverse sample to validate the findings, improve generalizability, and offer deeper insights regarding ChatGPT's effectiveness and acceptability.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In this study, respondents were given an informed consent form and asked to sign it, which provided a detailed description of the study's purpose and explained how their responses would be utilized. The form also included and explained the voluntary nature of the study. The respondents may withdraw at any time or opt not to participate without consequences. Additionally, the form put an emphasis on the fact that the researcher is a student, not a staff or faculty member at any university or institution. Furthermore, each respondent's identity was kept confidential. All data gathered was utilized solely for research purposes and, upon analysis, was stored securely for a reasonable period of time. Moreover, the researcher ensured that the questions used in the questionnaire were respectful and would not cause discomfort or harm to the respondents. Lastly, before data collection, the researcher sought approval from the principal of the school where the questionnaires would be administered to ensure that the study would be conducted in accordance with ethical principles.

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